

Victim of Its Own Success (?) – The European Union’s Anti-corruption Policy Advice in Ukraine Between Grand Visions and (Geo)political Realities

MICHAEL MARTIN RICHTER^{1,2} ¹Research Centre for East European Studies at the University of Bremen, Bremen ²Bremen International Graduate School of Social Sciences (BIGSSS), Bremen

Abstract

The European Union’s (EU) external governance enjoys significant attention in the literature. Yet its outcomes are usually assessed with reference to strategic documents or scholars’ self-designed criteria. This article contributes to the ongoing debate with a discourse analysis focusing on the perceptions of anti-corruption reform outcomes in Ukraine by actors on different levels in the EU. Simultaneously, structural factors are incorporated into the analysis. It demonstrates that although constant progress is officially proclaimed by the EU, even technical advisers disagree on how success in this crucial domain is understood and how to measure it. High-level representatives face a balancing act between conditionality demands, sovereignty limitations and geopolitical considerations. This explains the official signalling by the EU and the development of its rule-of-law reform conditionality. The outcome is a potential state of moral hazard and raise the question whether EU external governance has not become a victim of its ‘own success’.

Keywords: anti-corruption; conditionality; democracy promotion; EU; external governance; Ukraine

Introduction

The promotion of ‘governance by conditionality’ has a long-standing tradition in the relations of the European Union (EU) with its partners in the neighbourhood (Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier, 2004). This governance, also known as external governance, describes ‘institutionalized relationships, in which the partner countries commit themselves to approximate their domestic policies and legislation to the EU *acquis*’ (Lavenex and Schimmelfennig, 2011, p. 896). In Ukraine, the institutional framework of this relationship is particularly developed, as the country is the EU’s biggest single recipient of financial aid (Larsen, 2021). Moreover, Ukraine seeks not integration with but into the Union, that is, accession.

The designated objectives of this approximation, that is, ‘building a deep and sustainable democracy and a market economy’ (Association Agreement, 2014: preamble), have been only partially achieved in the opinion of most scholars (Matsiyevsky, 2018). However, the Association Agreement (AA) only lays out the final goals, without elaborating intermediate steps and a corresponding time horizon. This opened space for various subjective interpretations of where and why external governance progress stands in Ukraine and why. Correspondingly, little attention has been paid to the EU’s own assessment of this progress. This is particularly true with respect to the distinction between the political and technocratic levels in the EU as an institution, something that van Schendelen and van Schendelen (2010) call the ‘skeleton versus flesh-and-blood’.

This article contributes to the vast collection of studies seeking to analyse the EU's external governance performance (Baltag and Romanyszyn, 2017). It focuses on the overlooked understanding of success and the perception of outcomes by all layers of the EU. Such a discourse analysis brings the scholar closer to the 'origins of policies' (Tomic, 2013, p. 9). This article incorporates structural factors into its analysis. These are understood as 'enduring constraints [that] limit the options of political leaders and channel outcomes into a narrower range than would be expected from a focus on the personal preferences of leaders or the political views of the forces they represent' (D'Anieri, 2011, p. 28). This way, the divergence between subjective perception and external action is explained, which particularly concerns a perceived continuation of the same policy approach as put forwards by observers. The analysis is applied to anti-corruption reforms. This domain is particularly suitable, as it represents a good indication for the general reform progress, which is, however, subject to debates on its measurability. That only increases the importance of perceptions.

This analysis relies on semi-structured interviews with representatives from various levels and institutions within the EU as well as Ukrainian representatives from civil society and government that the author conducted just until the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022. It is complemented by an analysis of relevant primary and secondary literature. Although the article refers to the pre-war time, it generally fosters the understanding of the EU's policy approach and outcomes in Ukraine, including of shortcomings. It might therefore assist in formulating a successful post-war EU strategy. To proceed with its argument, first, the theoretical framework with the associated justification for this approach will be elaborated. Second, the methodology and the research design will be presented. Third, the research findings will be laid out and summarized in the last part.

1. Theoretical Framework

Although Ukraine has been granted official EU candidacy status under the dramatic conditions of Russia's war of aggression in 2022, before that, the literature had regarded it as a prime example of a country integrating with the EU without a real accession prospect (Schimmelfennig, 2015). As the literature stipulates, this limits the effectiveness of the conditionality mechanism due to the lack of credible benefits provided for compliance, which then fail to change the incentive structure of recipient governments (Schimmelfennig, 2015). This also concerns other forms of leverage in the anti-corruption realm that depend on the credibility of the prospect of membership (Kartal, 2014).

Moreover, the measurability of policy advice as such is limited, as 'no comparative [as for candidate countries] quantitative assessments for the ENP [Eastern Neighbourhood Programme]' are available (Schimmelfennig, 2017, p. 19). This also concerns Ukraine, where the previous Action Plan (AP) under the ENP was 'one of the few yardsticks which allow an assessment of the performance of the governments and public administration in Ukraine' (Wolczuk, 2009, pp. 208–209). After signing the AA, it got replaced by the Association Implementation Report (AIR). However, just as the AP, it is descriptive, without measurable and comparable benchmarks, and suffers from a lack of traceability between the different, mostly annual reports. This contrasts with enlargement processes.

For instance, in the Croatian case, there were 21 precise rule-of-law benchmarks set as preconditions for accession with a corresponding (political) timeline for completion (Grubisa, 2010).

Basic Approaches to EU External Governance

Despite the lack of effective comparative measures, the literature has extensively studied external governance outcomes. Lavenex and Schimmelfennig (2009) distinguish in this respect three analytical approaches: First, institutionalist arguments make the point that ‘external governance ... [is] ... shaped by internal EU modes of governance and rules’ (Lavenex and Schimmelfennig, 2009, p. 792). Its success is subsequently dependent on the ‘legalization and/or legitimacy’ of stipulated rules (Lavenex and Schimmelfennig, 2009, p. 802). Internal cohesiveness and consistency of policy provisions are key factors attributed to outcomes under this analytical strand (Schimmelfennig, 2015, p. 20). However, constraints, such as the EU’s bargaining power, also explain how internal unity affects results in external affairs (Da Conceição-Heldt and Meunier, 2014). As the literature argues, effectiveness is then a result of both internal factors and external constraints (Groen and Niemann, 2013).

This leads to the second set of analytical approaches, namely, power-based frameworks. They see the interaction between two competing, external actors in a country as decisive for the outcome of policy advice, that is, in the case of a country like Ukraine, the relative influence of the EU vis-à-vis Russia (Ademmer, 2016). The logic is a zero-sum game in which the gain of one actor is the loss of the other. Moscow is a constraining factor, and the stronger the interdependencies with a third country in a sector are, the less likely is the EU to transfer its rules in that domain (Dimitrova and Dragneva, 2009). This is known as ‘rival conditionality’ (Ademmer, 2016). However, the degree to which Russia can hamper EU rule adaptation in third countries is also contingent on other factors. For instance, ‘negative incentives that were not clearly linked to specific demands frequently made third countries seek shelter in compliance with EU policies to be eligible for (geo)political and economic alternatives’ (Ademmer, 2016, p. 207). This lack of specific demands closely resembles institutional explanations. Hence, just like the institutional approach was influenced by external factors, so the external channel is at least impacted by internal constellations of the respective other.

Lastly, the domestic approach explains the success of external governance by structural factors in the target country, arguing that ‘the impact of EU conditionality depends not only on the type of conditionality alone, but on how it resonates with the domestic context’ (Wolczuk, 2009, p. 208). Through this, different outcomes for the same set of EU policy advice across countries are expected. Not surprisingly, this approach has therefore been often applied to detect, compare and explain cross-country differences in external governance outcomes (Ademmer and Börzel, 2013). It also found usage in single-country case studies, not least in Ukraine (Králíková, 2022). For instance, civil society is seen by some as a factor explaining reform progress (Lutsevych, 2016), whilst others focus on the limitations of the civil society stemming from existing domestic, political economy structures (Cleary, 2016). These studies also distinguish between formal and factual implementation of EU rules and explain its subsequent level by the match

of it with domestic structures (Ademmer and Börzel, 2013). However, other studies show how policies with a high misfit might nevertheless lead to EU rule adaptation if powerful interests demand it (Langbein and Börzel, 2013).

Hybrid Approaches in Response to Analytical Shortcomings

Given conceptual and empirical shortcomings, more hybrid concepts have emerged, most notably, so-called 'transnational networks of democracy promotion' (Samokhvalov and Strelkov, 2021), which are also known in the literature as the 'sandwich method' (Nitsova et al., 2018). They see the outcome of external governance as promising when it is based on 'multiple channels of interaction between external actors and domestic state and non-state actors' (Langbein, 2014, p. 165). A similar conclusion has been drawn for the Ukrainian case, but with significant cross-sectoral variations (Nitsova et al., 2018). Particularly in spheres of strong resistance that nevertheless represent the core of 'Europeanization', such as anti-corruption reforms, these transnational networks are said to be (still) too weak to overcome domestic resistance (Harasymiw, 2019).

These networks span 'high-level diplomats and politicians, technical experts, civil society actors and media' (Samokhvalov and Strelkov, 2021, p. 810). Through this, they intersect with at least the institutional and domestic explanations approach. The rationale of a hybrid analytical framework gets strengthened by questions of agency. Traditional approaches depart from the 'unity actor' assumption present in the International Relations scholarship (Lavenex and Schimmelfennig, 2009). However, when referring to *internal* cohesion, institutional approaches mostly make the distinction between the EU and its member states (Schimmelfennig, 2015). Only recently has the power dynamic between technocratic and political layers within the EU as an institution gained more prominence, but so far exclusively with respect to issues concerning member states (Kelemen and Pavone, 2022). Yet, as analytical studies on the EU's effect on good governance reforms show, there are significant differences in the actual mechanisms at play between countries with and without an accession status (Kartal, 2014).

Summarizing the scholarship on EU external governance, it was therefore argued that 'scholarly achievements [so far] could not offer greater clarity and systematization with regards to both the influence of structure- and agency-related factors' (Schumacher, 2017, p. 7). In a related fashion, a Ukrainian scholar posed the 'fascinating question' of 'why [...] EU, and individual European countries are still devoting effort to help Ukraine combat political corruption in the face of years of failure' (Harasymiw, 2019, p. 304). At the same time, the author *assumes* 'geopolitical considerations [are] involved'. This is seconded by other authors, such as Schimmelfennig (2021), however without providing any explanation or reference.

2. Methodology

This is exemplary of the traditional focus of EU studies on 'understand[ing] [the] reality' of EU actions rather than explaining them (Carta, 2021). This is arguably also the reason for the previously mentioned gap in the literature. To bridge it, a discourse analysis of the

EU's own understanding seems promising as it allows 'scholars to focus simultaneously on *textual and contextual elements, agency-related and structural characteristics and their dynamic reciprocal relationships*' (Carta, 2021).

Tomic (2013) shows the relevance of this approach in the EU context, as formal and de facto decisions are made on different levels. Hence, within one institution, 'the knowledge of the events and situations ... [is] ... filtered through and by the various levels of recipients' (Tomic, 2013, p. 10). A discourse analysis therefore allows to get to the 'origins of policies' through considering 'the ideas and meanings of the material reality' (Tomic, 2013, p. 9). However, these ideas and meanings alone are not sufficient, as 'contingent policy outcomes will not necessarily coherently reflect the original intentions of actors'. In addition, the context or 'social structure in which discursive practices occur' must be considered (Carta and Morin, 2016). Based on these factors, EU foreign policy outcomes have been *explained* by 'semantic struggles between two discursive coalitions' (Carta, 2021).

Case Selection

Although this approach has increasingly grown in popularity (see, e.g., Carta and Morin, 2016, for an entire collection), studies in the external governance context using this method are scarce. This scarcity also concerns the differences between the technocratic and political levels in the EU as an institution, which constitutes, as elaborated before, a striking gap in the literature. Assessing therefore the case of (high-level) anti-corruption reforms in Ukraine, this study contributes to fill this gap and provides *explanations* for the observed conditionality outcome in Ukraine. This choice stems from theoretical as well as practical considerations. First, Ukraine is the biggest recipient of EU aid amongst all non-EU countries. Through five Macro-Financial Assistance (MFA) programmes alone, the EU provided \$5 bn. of support to Kyiv between 2014 and the beginning of the Russian invasion in February 2022 (European Commission, 2022a). A sixth one was approved as an emergency measure afterwards but is out of the scope of this article. Through this, the EU has a well-developed and extensive institutional infrastructure of financial and technical support in Ukraine.

Second, this work focuses explicitly on high-level anti-corruption reforms, hence limiting the scope to actions on the 'conditionality' dimension. This stems from the crucial role of these reforms in the Europeanization path of Ukraine. It is a cross-cutting issue that acts as a suitable proxy for the level of overall institutional development (Lederman et al., 2005). Although being an important issue, academia debates over measurement approaches of corruption (Andersson and Heywood, 2009). This only underlines the suitability of a discourse analysis as a step forward to understand and explain EU external governance efforts and outcomes in this domain in Ukraine, as the perceived lack of objective measurements bears huge potential for semantic contestation amongst actors.

Data Collection and Analytical Approach

To reach its designated aims, a qualitative analysis based on semi-structured interviews, that is, with the help of an earlier prepared questionnaire that was flexibly expanded during the conversation, was conducted. Six current and former representatives of all relevant EU institutions and member-state agencies, as well as six representatives of the public and

non-governmental sector in Ukraine, were interviewed. The rationale behind bringing in non-EU participants was to gather insider assessments from people closely involved with EU agents to introduce a third-party perspective on the self-assessment of EU representatives and act as a potential corrective to inaccurate subjective assessments. The decision to 'get an outside perspective from key stakeholders' has been applied in other studies assessing EU rule-of-law mechanisms and developments (Kelemen and Pavone, 2022, p. 16). Moreover, although external governance is assumed to be conceptually 'Eurocentric' (Schimmelfennig, 2021), by bringing in the perspective of the Ukrainian side, a certain decentralization is achieved whilst keeping the focus on the perception of EU agents.

All interviews, for which an official ethics clearance was obtained on 21 July 2021, were conducted between October 2021 and January 2022 in English and lasted from 60 to 90 min (for a full methodological description, see Richter [2023]). For each interview, explicit consent was acquired, and the desired quotation rule established beforehand. However, due to the sensitivity of the issue in the current context, all interviewees are anonymized. The interviews were transcribed and coded, and its content was analysed using MAXQDA. The coding scheme followed an inductive and deductive approach, relying on an earlier prepared framework from the literature analysis, focusing on the understanding and measure of success, perceptions of outcomes, perceptions of the 'Other' and explanations of differences. This was flexibly expanded throughout the analytical process with an increasing number of retrieved factors, such as the identification of the realist versus idealist perspectives.

The interview process was halted by the Russian invasion of Ukraine, which limited the number of respondents. A later commencement was discarded as the EU–Ukraine context changed considerably as visible in the candidacy status and with it, also perceptions, which is outlined in the conclusion. Although small, an insightful sample was obtained that showed two perceptual camps and approaches that can in this form also be found in official documents, which increases the validity of the results due to triangulation. These official documents included AIRs, EU Court of Auditors (CoA) documents, press releases of the investigated institutions, Venice Commission reports and Group of States against Corruption reports. For even further triangulation and contextualization, secondary analytical pieces were used, such as the literature presented in Section 1 together with related works, reports of Ukrainian civil society organizations (CSOs) and Western think tanks.

3. Analytical Part

To explain the high-level anti-corruption conditionality process of the EU in Ukraine, this section is divided into four parts. First, the entire process is mapped and laid out to detect crucial interactions and agents. Then, the official assessment of the outcome and the ways it is measured are presented. It therefore starts at the end of the policy process from the publicly communicated discourse. In the third step, the understanding of and different ways to measure success by actors in the policy process are presented with the aim to detect discrepancies amongst the actors. This part also presents the different 'discursive coalitions' that exist in the process. This also concerns the last part, in which the structural context and therefore also constraints, particularly in the perception of the 'Other', are laid out and elaborated.

The Decision-Making Process of Policy Advice in Ukraine on the Example of MFA Conditionalities

In most high-level decisions, political actors rely on the input from technical advisors based in the specially designated agencies. The case of the MFA mechanism, usually seen as the main way to exercise conditionality, is illustrative for that, and its process can be depicted in Figure 1.

As is visible, the execution of conditionality is a task of the Ukrainian side. It is officially being put forward by the political level in the EU, depending on which framework this conditionality falls. The MFA programmes, and their associated conditionalities, are being run by Directorate General (DG) for Economics and Finances (ECFIN) of the European Commission (Interview 1). All MFAs require a memorandum of understanding, in which commitments from the Ukrainian side are highlighted. These commitments broadly mirror the more general provisions of the AA and are supposed to bring the country closer to their fulfilment. The input for these conditionality prescriptions comes from different stakeholders, not least the EU's own technical advisors on the ground as well as Ukrainian CSOs. One technical adviser elaborated on this exchange of information:

We have a task force working group where we are sitting together with DG ECFIN colleagues and have a constant exchange on a biweekly or on demand basis to exchange not only on the strategic direction or the actual formulation of the conditionalities but also on the assessment of the implementation and the progress. (Interview 6)

Additional input comes from CSOs, which, in the Ukrainian case, have their key weakness in advocating for political decisions (Palyvoda et al., 2018). Whilst Western partners provide this push, Ukrainian CSOs provide the necessary knowledge of the 'local context'. Through this, they can monitor the nuanced progress and quickly detect shortcomings in the execution of conditionalities (Interview 1). This input is being put forward to technical advisers, who then filter it and bring it to the higher level. There, a political

Figure 1: Conceptualization of the Macro-Financial Assistance mechanism in Ukraine. Own presentation. CSOs, civil society organizations; EU, European Union; UA, Ukrainian. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/terms-and-conditions)]

‘translation’ mechanism follows that considers various constraints. Based on that, the EU officially issues a yearly review of the overall rule-of-law progress and decides on the disbursement of further tranches under a working MFA programme.

The Official Narrative

These official documents contrast with the presented perspective of scholars as progress is a constant description in the EU’s official assessment of reforms in Ukraine. Already in 2015, it certified ‘that Ukraine made some progress ... with notably *substantial achievements on deep and sustainable democracy, including on ... anti-corruption legislation*’ (European Commission, 2015, p. 3). The 2017 AIR noted that ‘considerable legislative reforms have taken place in the fight against corruption ... [and] work on implementation of anti-corruption efforts continued over the past year, while further substantial work is still outstanding’ (European Commission, 2017, p. 2). In 2018, it noted that ‘reforms also advanced in the areas of the judiciary and anti-corruption’ (European Commission, 2018, p. 1). In 2019, it attested that ‘in the area of justice, rule of law and the fight against corruption, Ukraine continued to build an effective institutional framework’ (European Commission, 2019, p. 2).

According to one EU adviser, in its official narrative, the European Commission portrays anti-corruption reforms as ‘almost done, but a bit more time needed, and a bit more money ...’ (Interview 12). However, oftentimes, progress from 1 year gets eroded in a subsequent year. The latest AIR, which focuses on 2021, acknowledges that ‘Ukrainian reform efforts in relation to the rule of law and the fight against corruption have in 2021 been focused on *restoring legislation* intended to guarantee the independence and effectiveness of the anti-corruption institutional framework’ (European Commission, 2022b, p. 8). As one observer noted, therefore, ‘the EU has become like the Ukrainian authorities as they want to show short-term success. But this success [then] is a minor output’ (Interview 7). This observation is interesting as it echoes Stegniy’s (2011) assessment that the EU’s policy towards Ukraine a decade ago was characterized by ‘short-sightedness’.

This ‘success’ comprises mostly the anti-corruption infrastructure, which respondents identified univocally as a self-declared success of EU anti-corruption reforms advice to Ukraine. It consists of the National Agency on Corruption Prevention, National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU), Specialized Anti-Corruption Prosecutor’s Office (SAPO) and the High Anti-Corruption Court (HACC). However, both current and former employees and third parties broadly agreed that these institutions were being undermined and therefore represent (still) a limited success story (Interviews 1, 7, 10 and 12).

Even between European institutions, entirely different perceptions with respect to the official assessment of this outcome are visible, which is symbolized by the Court of Auditors report from 2021. It generated significant salience in policy circles, and both the CoA and the European Commission issued press statements on its release day, 23 September 2021. The European Court of Auditors’ (2021) release was titled ‘EU Support for Reforms in Ukraine Ineffective in Fighting Grand Corruption’, whilst the European Commission’s reads ‘Ukraine’s Fight Against High-Level Corruption: EU Support Instrumental but More Results Needed’ (European Commission, 2021). The former is unsurprisingly negative in its assessment, whilst the Commission ‘welcomes the Court’s finding that a significant

number of EU support actions in Ukraine's fight against corruption assisted in *moving the reform process forward*. In its reasoning, the Commission highlights the fact that 'in line with international best practice, supporting these [anti-corruption] institutions was instrumental in bringing the lacking institutional infrastructure to Ukraine – an indispensable prerequisite to tackling corruption successfully. As a result, the anti-corruption architecture in Ukraine is now complete'. Visibly, the CoA emphasizes the outcomes of institutions, and the Commission the institutional design as such.

Looking into official EU documents, especially at the AIRs, on how these outcomes are assessed *over time*, a non-stringent picture is retrieved: In 2019, the AIR described the conviction rate of the anti-corruption infrastructure, with 31 since the inception of NABU, as 'very low' (European Commission, 2019, p. 10). In 2020, with cumulative 41 convictions, it only noted that 'with HACC now operational, a higher rate of convictions is anticipated' (European Commission, 2020, p. 10). Although it then argued in 2022 that '[t]he HACC continued to build a solid track record. After two years of its activity, guilty verdicts have been passed pertaining inter alia to Members of Parliament, representatives of local councils and judges', it entirely abstained from reporting numbers of both cases administered and convictions made (European Commission, 2022a, p. 8). Moreover, in none of the years did it talk about the quality of convictions nor about what a sufficient conviction rate would be. This is also important considering reported attempts to overturn HACC rulings (Transparency International, 2021a) or transfer cases to ordinary courts (Transparency International, 2021b). Hence, it does not allow to objectively track and conclude based on these findings how 'successful' or not these established institutions are for the EU. The underlying lack of 'baselines, targets, [and] continuity' (Interview 7) is a general point of criticism with respect to the AIRs shared by some of the respondents. Summarizing it, a very positive yet non-coherent official narrative of high-level anti-corruption reform progress, and the associated role of the EU in it, is presented by the EU to the public.

Understanding of Success by Each Designated Actor

Assessing subsequently the perceptions of specific EU agents, potential differences and therefore intervening factors can be detected. They then explain the translation process between the technocratic and political levels (Arrows 1 and 2 in Figure 1) and the formation of perceptual differences. As corruption is difficult to measure, the distinction between perceived 'reality' and 'fiction' plays an important role, as argued by an EU advisor:

On different layers of the EU structures, on political but also on the managerial layers, the overall judgment is of great importance. What is going on? What is real? And what is virtual? It is a puzzle and that makes it kind of difficult. We are here auditing the performance and that is maybe very subjective. (Interview 6)

Continuing, this adviser elaborates, in the context of policy advice outcomes, the need to distinguish between the success of the advice and the success of the underlying reform: 'The success for my advice is the advice is being taken aboard and implemented and this is a success. But it doesn't mean that necessarily the reform will be successful for various reasons, for instance external factors' (Interview 6). This already highlights that policy

advice is subject to different intervening forces. Another policy adviser set the benchmark even lower and argued that:

One thing we have to prove is that corruption has not increased by our work, and this is something that I can guarantee, and this is measured all of the time – at least we do not make the situation worse. (Interview 8)

For a former EU policy advisor in the anti-corruption realm, the EU's actions represent to large extent a 'ticking boxes exercise ... work in a bureaucratic structure where employees are focused on running programs, not necessarily deliver outcomes' (Interview 1). With respect to the understanding of success, this respondent added that 'there is no definition of success and that goes back to the European Court of Auditors report. They ask what is the end goal [of EU anti-corruption policy in Ukraine]? It is nowhere to find'.

One policy adviser nevertheless argued that 'there is not one definition of success. But we really need to look at the core reforms and then one will see a reduction of the space for corruption as a by-product of systemic reforms in many areas' (Interview 6). This technical adviser therefore perceives the outcome in line with the official narrative. However, another technical policy advisor illustrated the reform outcome, in line with much of the criticism, followingly:

We can organise an excellent anti-corruption infrastructure, we can show it like in a zoo: here we have plenty of anti-corruption state authorities, here we have special anti-corruption state authorities, here we have special institutions and in that corner, we will have in the nearest future anti-corruption prisons. But what we have at the moment are no ... results from these cases ... So, for me much more significant is the real situation because of course we can provide information that we have this and that but two days ago Transparency International published the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) and Ukraine moved five to ten positions down. That is the real situation. (Interview 12)

Interestingly, these different perceptions mirror almost exactly those of the semantic struggle between the Commission and the CoA on the day of the release of the auditing report. The reference to the CPI is also noteworthy, as another representative remarked that '[EU anti-corruption policy advice in Ukraine is] sort of a ticking boxes exercise because corruption in Ukraine is such an issue, and in particular grand corruption, that the EU should monitor it at least regularly and there is no specific report for that' (Interview 7). This already hints at cross-institutional discursive coalitions.

The problem of understanding success in the first place gets complicated by the problem of how to measure it and what a potential reference point or benchmark should be. One insider noted:

They [EU institutions] are just reporting some developments ... or ... outputs, like the adoption of laws that do not change much. Ukraine doesn't move closer to the so-called Copenhagen criteria, because they should be the benchmark in reality. (Interview 7)

Looking at representatives within the EU, the lack of a mutually agreed reference point and correspondingly differences in ways to assess outcomes becomes visible. One technical adviser 'see[s] a reform success in terms of the number of cases adjudicated and processed by the anti-corruption investigation chain, in this case NABU, SAPO, the HACC'. The respondent therefore echoes the official narrative and perception of the EU. This

person is, however, simultaneously ‘not talking about convictions because [one] cannot do that; that would go against the presumption of innocence’ (Interview 6). Comparing this to the assessment of the responding putting forward the metaphor of the zoo, the previously mentioned tension in perceptions becomes once again visible: Whereas for one advisor, the successful operationalization of institutions means the processing of cases (Interview 6), for another advisor, it is the factual conviction rate of these cases and therefore making the person conclude that much progress is perceived to be merely showcased (Interview 12). Notably, this tension exists not only within the same EU institution but also on the side of Ukrainian CSO representatives that can also be divided into these two camps (Interview 11, Interview 5 vs. Interview 10).

Explaining the Difference Between Official Narrative and ‘Lived Reality’

Having demonstrated the difference in perceptions of outcomes and definitions of success even amongst people representing the same level in the same institution, the question of how these differences amongst these ‘discursive coalitions’ and the emergence of the official narrative can be explained arises. First, technical aspects, that is, issues with the communication or retrieval of information, can be seen as neglectable. Even the programme manager questioning the EU’s broader results admitted that ‘we at have a clear and strict project planning process’ (Interview 2). Rather, another technical advisor added ‘our input is of course extremely important, but there might be other considerations that might overshadow the technical aspects of those assessments’ (Interview 6). And, in contrast to its official narrative, most respondents share the opinion that even high-level politicians on the EU side, not least by being equipped with insights from their technical staff, understand the problems and shortcomings of anti-corruption policy in Ukraine (Interview 1).

Explaining therefore the outcome, that is, the official narrative, the importance of structural factors and ‘images of “Others” ’ were incorporated, as they allow to establish the context in which this discourse takes place. That is because an image ‘influences the diagnosis of the situation, and [...] leads the actor to favor certain types of actions’ (Chaban and Elgström, 2021). In the case of EU anti-corruption reforms in Ukraine, two particular ‘Others’ are of relevance – Ukraine itself and Russia as the main adversary in the neighbourhood.

Starting with Ukraine, one high-level representative of the European Commission noted, after being confronted with the allegations of being too soft in its yearly assessment and missing clear benchmarks, that:

Concrete targets are dangerous. Authorities might reach the target and stop there. They just do the agreed bare minimum as you must agree on something because it must be verified. That is to some extent a problem that we cannot solve because we need verifiable conditions for our payments under the MFA. Therefore, the impression that reforms have become a ticking boxes exercise is because the authorities themselves do not own their reforms to the extent that they should. This is an issue of internal consciousness and willingness of Ukrainian authorities. (Interview 2)

Hence, the responsibility for a lack of far-stretching execution is put on Ukrainian authorities and their perceived lack of will. Another EU advisor shared this point of view by elaborating:

The 'high political influence' [in Ukraine is the reason for a lack of a breakthrough]. That is why we are still focused on fighting against petty but not grand corruption. That's why the main preventive tools still [exist] on paper only. That is why Ukraine is since 2017 without [a] National Anti-corruption Strategy. That is why [it] faced crises made by the decisions of Ukraine's Constitutional Court on anti-corruption reforms. (Interview 12)

The image of the Ukrainian authorities is therefore one of the resisting far-stretching reforms in the anti-corruption context. It is, however, important to see it in conjunction with the 'sovereignty' aspect that the EU upholds in this context. It was frequently mentioned by the interviewees as being a clear limitation of the EU's leverage on Ukraine. It can also be understood as the matter of ownership and agency for reforms. This directly touches upon the domestic explanation strand of external governance outcomes, and Ukrainian experts have noted themselves that 'the ownership and the work is on Ukraine's shoulders, everything else is simply not working' (Interview 10). One advisor elaborated that 'one can only ... create conditionality to the extent that it does not touch Ukraine's sovereignty; and that's something that you have to take into account, as it is a very concrete thin line' (Interview 8).

This sovereignty aspect leads to a general problem, described as 'vexing ambiguity' in the literature (Bermeo, 2016, p. 15). In the context of anti-reform pushes, it symbolizes the difficulty to distinguish between sincere decisions made by courts overruling some reform provisions and those made for the sake of vested interests. This ambiguity leads to a general limitation of the 'leverage' channel because the previously mentioned 'thin line' is oftentimes subject to interpretation and not independently defined. Ukrainian politicians have repeatedly run campaigns against conditionalities under the slogan of defending sovereignty. For instance, the previous presidential administration opposed the participation of independent, international experts in the selection procedure of judges for the HACC in the form of a Public Council of International Experts due to supposed national sovereignty infringements of such an entity (Krasnosilka, 2018). This was a central cornerstone strongly advocated for by CSOs, the EU and the International Monetary Fund. In the end, reformists succeeded with their postulates, but the Council was set up with a limited duration of 6 years as to strike the balance between ensuring the initial independence of this central institution without a too severe (perceived) impact on national sovereignty (Council of Europe, 2021).

The centrality of Ukraine's sovereignty and agency for reforms was unanimously shared by all respondents, creating therefore a common understanding with respect to this contextual factor. A Ukrainian CSO representative added another image of Ukraine that was not represented by any of the respondents as such: 'there are a lot of voices in the EU countries inspired by Russia telling that Ukraine is a failure' (Interview 5).

The aspect of Russia refers to the geopolitical realm, in which clear differences amongst the respondents were noticeable. On the one hand, the geopolitical importance of Ukraine for the EU was stressed by all interviewees. As such, respondents highlighted the 'enormous, geopolitical importance' (Interview 8) or 'very complicated geopolitical structure' (Interview 5) of Ukraine. This aspect can explain the gap between reality, as perceived by many insiders, including policy advisers themselves, and the official narrative. One EU civil servant noted openly in this respect:

We would be ill advised if we wouldn't take geopolitical considerations into account in the decisions that we are taking. If we took the Russian narrative that Ukraine is a failed state and reforms have led to nothing good in the country, then this obviously has a negative connotation and negative impact that we don't want. But in terms of the conditionalities that doesn't mean that we are too soft or that we would simply disregard the conditionalities that we have set up. But it needs to be a balanced approach, taking into account [geo]political considerations, otherwise it would eventually be even counterproductive, [as with] that narrative we would easily feed Russian propaganda. (Interview 6)

A soft official narrative therefore prevents creating the image of Ukraine as a failed state in the public realm. As a result, a high-level EU bureaucrat admitted that 'there is some truth to it that we have to keep Ukraine afloat for geopolitical reasons' (Interview 2). This assessment strikingly contrasts with how some other insiders perceive the geopolitical aspect and the role of Russia. One acknowledged 'the geopolitical importance [of Ukraine]' but understood it as an 'important card in the game of reality and virtuality [that] must be clearly separated [...] from reforming the country' (Interview 7). Rather, the respondent added that Ukraine is 'a perfect case to change the trend' (of the global rise of authoritarianism) and a 'quick success in internal reforms is the strongest card in the war with Russia' (Interview 7). This was seconded in a similar fashion by a former EU advisor (Interview 1). Therefore, a discursive coalition of 'realists' that sees Russia as a reason to soften its official signalling faces in a semantic struggle a coalition of 'idealists' that perceives the Russia factor as being a reason to be particularly resolute with the public signals that the EU sends out to exercise the needed pressure.

Therefore, just as the EU must walk on a thin line with respect to sovereignty, it needs to factor in the external signals that it sends out with its assessments and conditionalities. Two opposite ways with respect to the latter become apparent, although official narratives are clearly aligning with the version to soften the assessment of outcomes. This becomes visible by analysing the AIRs, in which the aspect of external relations is also prominently represented, for instance, by arguing that 'the illegal annexation of Crimea and Sevastopol by the Russian Federation and the conflict in the east of the country provoked by Russia's destabilising actions have continued to pose significant challenges to Ukraine's reform process from a political and economic perspective' (European Commission, 2017, p. 2). This happened in the same year where it attested that 'considerable legislative reforms have taken place in the fight against corruption' (European Commission, 2017, p. 2).

Whilst sending out these soft signals, a corresponding question is whether Ukraine represents a case of moral hazard according to the 'too big to fail' mantra and whether it did not become a victim of its *own success*? This particularly refers to the 'realists' and notably to the high-level respondent who admitted that geopolitical reasons keep up the support practically unconditionally. This person assured that this was no reason that conditionality was being too soft, however without further elaborating how this moral hazard equation was solved. Notably, the importance of a membership prospect, something that the literature highlights as a central variable in explaining external governance outcomes, was not perceived as important to be as the other factors. This applies to both EU and Ukrainian representatives. Rather, it was seen as *one* possible 'facilitator of reforms' (Interview 6) and an additional motivation (Interview 12). Other insiders saw this debate around membership, particularly those from the camp of the 'idealists', as an excuse for a lack of reform progress (Interviews 1 and 7).

Conclusions

Has the EU's external governance in Ukraine become a victim of its *own* success? This article contributes to the explanation of its processes and outcomes by conducting a discourse analysis, combining agency-related and structural factors. So far, studies on EU external governance lack an assessment of the inner workings of the EU and its understanding of policy processes and outcomes that this study puts forward. Simultaneously, much of the 'traditional' literature on external governance focuses on the notion of 'internal cohesiveness' by evaluating the EU and its member states separately, but again hardly on the EU as an institution and its different layers.

As this study shows, the measurement of *ongoing* success is not defined by the EU for external audiences and the lack of internally agreed definitions and traceable benchmarks is an important finding. Through it, even advisors on the *same level in the same institution define success and perceive outcomes differently*. This way, some technical advisors are more aligned in their perception with the higher level than with their technocratic colleagues highlighting the existence of vertical 'discursive coalitions'. This highlights the risk of using a framework with a strict dichotomy between these layers in analytical approaches to *external governance*. Notably, these differences also exist across EU institutions, as the official press releases on the CoA report demonstrate.

The differences in perceptions and its consequences are a result of different structural considerations and interpretations of the geopolitical 'Other' that agents seem to factor in. Whilst for some representatives, particularly those at the political level, the geopolitical risk of being too harsh outweighs the risk of being too soft in the conditionality provisions, others see reform progress as a channel for geopolitical success. However, it might be said that the latter are not facing the same constraints as the former. Political representatives carry the burden of the political translation process in which they must cope with various structural limitations, particularly geopolitical ones. As these did not change until very recently, the continuation of the same official narrative can be explained by this factor.

Yet, despite almost constant appraisal in official documents, even political representatives admit shortcomings. However, according to the proverb 'success has many fathers, failure is an orphan', they see the main reason for this on the Ukrainian side. As agency is undoubtedly on the side of Kyiv and sovereignty a unanimously accepted limitation by all respondents, Ukrainian elites are likely acting in this respect rationally to maximize their own benefit. Knowing that 'there is some truth to it that we [the EU] have to keep Ukraine afloat for geopolitical reasons', elites in Kyiv can engage in significant reform imitation. The actual victim of the EU's *own success* might therefore be the credibility of conditionality and moral hazard the outcome.

An obvious limitation to the conclusions drawn is the rather small sample size, as elaborated in Section 2. Future studies should, thus, aim to cover a larger and broader sample in the new context. This new context relates to the geopolitical landscape, which changed because of Russia's large-scale invasion, effectively diminishing Moscow's influence in post-war Ukraine. Applying the framework of this study, this new reality offers a more positive outlook by suggesting that significant obstacles to reform may disappear: The prevailing 'realist' perspective will possibly align with the more optimistic 'idealist' viewpoint within the EU. This holds the potential to transform geopolitical constraints into

catalysts for reform. This ongoing shift will have already played a role in bringing about the EU membership prospect for Ukraine. The prospect will compel the EU to establish tangible and measurable long-term benchmarks, which will foster ‘internal cohesiveness’ within the EU in defining success and shaping perceptions of outcomes. As a result, a genuine partnership based on effective conditionality may emerge, ultimately leading Ukraine to pursue integration *into* the EU rather than mere association.

Acknowledgements

The author expresses his gratitude to Heiko Pleines, Michael Rochlitz, Margarita Balmaceda, the BIGSSS colloquium participants, and three anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments. Moreover, he is thankful to all interviewees of his research project for their openness and readiness to share their insights. Furthermore, he appreciates the opportunity given to him by the funding of the EU HORIZON 2020 Innovative Training Network “MARKETS” (MSCA grant no 861034).

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Correspondence:

Michael Martin Richter, Research Centre for East European Studies at the University of Bremen, Klagenfurter Strasse 8, 28359 Bremen, Germany.

email: richterm@uni-bremen.de; michael.richter@coleurope.eu

References

- Ademmer, E. (2016) *Russia's Impact on EU Policy Transfer to the Post-Soviet Space: The Contested Neighborhood* (Routledge).
- Ademmer, E. and Börzel, T.A. (2013) ‘Migration, Energy and Good Governance in the EU’s Eastern Neighbourhood’. *Europe – Asia Studies*, Vol. 65, No. 4, pp. 581–608.
- Andersson, S. and Heywood, P.M. (2009) ‘The Politics of Perception: Use and Abuse of Transparency International’s Approach to Measuring Corruption’. *Political Studies*, Vol. 57, No. 4, pp. 746–767.
- Association Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and Ukraine of the other part (2014) ‘Official Journal of the European Union’, L 161.
- Baltag, D. and Romanyshyn, I. (2017) ‘The Challenge of Analysing the Performance of the European Neighbourhood Policy 1’. In Schumacher, T., Marchetti, A. and Demmelhuber, T. (eds) *The Routledge Handbook on the European Neighbourhood Policy* (Routledge), pp. 39–49.
- Bermeo, N. (2016) ‘On Democratic Backsliding’. *Journal of Democracy*, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 5–19.
- Carta, C. (2021) ‘Discourse Analytical Approaches and the Study of EU External Action’. In Gstöhl, S. and Schunz, S. (eds) *The External Action of the European Union: Concepts, Approaches, Theories* (Bloomsbury Publishing).
- Carta, C. and Morin, J.F. (eds) (2016) *EU Foreign Policy Through the Lens of Discourse Analysis: Making Sense of Diversity* (Routledge).
- Chaban, N. and Elgström, O. (2021) ‘Theorizing External Perceptions of the EU’. In Gstöhl, S. and Schunz, S. (eds) *The External Action of the European Union: Concepts, Approaches, Theories* (Bloomsbury Publishing).
- Cleary, L. (2016) ‘Half Measures and Incomplete Reforms: The Breeding Ground for a Hybrid Civil Society in Ukraine’. *Journal of Southeast European and Black Sea*, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 7–23.

- Council of Europe (2021) 'Ukraine: Venice Commission Publishes Two Urgent Opinions' [Press Release]. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/portal/-/ukraine-venice-commission-recommendations-on-ethics-council-draft-legislation>
- Da Conceição-Heldt, E. and Meunier, S. (2014) 'Speaking With a Single Voice: Internal Cohesiveness and External Effectiveness of the EU in Global Governance'. *Journal of European Public Policy*, Vol. 21, No. 7, pp. 961–979.
- D'Anieri, P. (2011) 'Structural Constraints in Ukrainian Politics'. *East European Politics and Societies*, Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 28–46.
- Dimitrova, A. and Dragneva, R. (2009) 'Constraining External Governance: Interdependence With Russia and the CIS as Limits to the EU's Rule Transfer in the Ukraine'. *Journal of European Public Policy*, Vol. 16, No. 6, pp. 853–872.
- European Commission (2015) 'Joint Staff Working Document – Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in Ukraine Progress in 2014 and Recommendations for Actions'. https://eeas.europa.eu/archives/docs/enp/pdf/2015/ukraine-enp-report-2015_en.pdf
- European Commission (2017) 'Joint Staff Working Document – Association Implementation Report on Ukraine'. <https://edz.bib.uni-mannheim.de/edz/pdf/swd/2017/swd-2017-0376-en.pdf>
- European Commission (2018) 'Joint Staff Working Document – Association Implementation Report on Ukraine'. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2018_association_implementation_report_on_ukraine.pdf
- European Commission (2019) 'Joint Staff Working Document – Association Implementation Report on Ukraine'. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/association-implementation-report-ukraine-2019_en
- European Commission (2020) 'Joint Staff Working Document – Association Implementation Report on Ukraine'. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/joint-staff-working-document-association-implementation-report-ukraine_en
- European Commission (2021) 'Ukraine's Fight Against High-Level Corruption: EU Support Instrumental but More Results Needed' [Press Release]. https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/news/ukraines-fight-against-high-level-corruption-eu-support-instrumental-more-results-needed-2021-09-23_en
- European Commission (2022a) 'Joint Staff Working Document – Association Implementation Report on Ukraine'. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/joint-staff-working-document-%E2%80%93-93-2021-association-implementation-report-ukraine_en
- European Commission (2022b) 'European Commission Disburses First Tranche of the New €1 Billion Macro-financial Assistance for Ukraine' [Press Release]. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_22_4783
- European Court of Auditors (2021) 'EU Support for Reforms in Ukraine Ineffective in Fighting Grand Corruption' [Press Release]. <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/Pages/NewsItem.aspx?nid=15711>
- Groen, L. and Niemann, A. (2013) 'The European Union at the Copenhagen Climate Negotiations: A Case of Contested EU Actorness and Effectiveness'. *International Relations*, Vol. 27, No. 3, pp. 308–324.
- Grubisa, D. (2010) 'Anti-corruption Policy in Croatia: Benchmark for EU Accession'. *Politička misao*, Vol. 47, No. 05, pp. 69–95.
- Harasymiw, B. (2019) 'Civil Society as an Anti-corruption Actor in Post-Euromaidan Ukraine'. *Canadian Slavonic Papers*, Vol. 61, No. 3, pp. 288–320.
- Kartal, M. (2014) 'Accounting for the Bad Apples: The EU's Impact on National Corruption Before and After Accession'. *Journal of European Public Policy*, Vol. 21, No. 6, pp. 941–959.
- Kelemen, R.D. and Pavone, T. (2022) *Where Have the Guardians Gone? Law Enforcement and the Politics of Supranational Forbearance in the European Union* (APSA Preprints).

- Králiková, M. (2022) 'Importing EU Norms: The Case of Anti-corruption Reform in Ukraine'. *Journal of European Integration*, Vol. 44, No. 2, pp. 245–260.
- Krasnosil'ska, A. (2018) 'Why Poroshenko's Anti-corruption Court Is a Sham Proposal'. *Atlantic Council*. <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/ukrainealert/why-poroshenko-s-anti-corruption-court-is-a-sham/>
- Langbein, J. (2014) 'European Union Governance Towards the Eastern Neighbourhood: Transcending or Redrawing Europe's East–West Divide?' *Journal of Common Market Studies*, Vol. 52, No. 1, pp. 157–174.
- Langbein, J. and Börzel, T.A. (2013) 'Introduction: Explaining Policy Change in the European Union's Eastern Neighbourhood'. *Europe-Asia Studies*, Vol. 65, No. 4, pp. 571–580.
- Larsen, H. (2021) 'Dilemmas of Aiding Ukraine'. *Survival*, Vol. 63, No. 1, pp. 161–178.
- Lavenex, S. and Schimmelfennig, F. (2009) 'EU Rules Beyond EU Borders: Theorizing External Governance in European Politics'. *Journal of European Public Policy*, Vol. 16, No. 6, pp. 791–812.
- Lavenex, S. and Schimmelfennig, F. (2011) 'EU democracy promotion in the neighbourhood: from leverage to governance?'. *Democratization*, Vol. 18, No. 2, pp. 885–909.
- Lederman, D., Loayza, N.V. and Soares, R.R. (2005) 'Accountability and Corruption: Political Institutions Matter'. *Economics and Politics*, Vol. 17, No. 1, pp. 1–35.
- Lutsevych, O. (2016) 'Civil Society Versus Captured State: A Winning Strategy for Sustainable Change'. *Development in Practice*, Vol. 26, No. 5, pp. 646–656.
- Matsiyevsky, Y. (2018) 'Revolution Without Regime Change: The Evidence From the Post-Euromaidan Ukraine'. *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, Vol. 51, No. 4, pp. 349–359.
- Nitsova, S., Pop-Eleches, G. and Robertson, G. (2018) *Revolution and Reform in Ukraine: Evaluating Four Years of Reform* (PONARS Eurasia).
- Palyvoda, L., Kuprii, N. and Bikla, O. (2018) *Status and Dynamics of Civil Society Organizations Development in Ukraine in 2002–2018: Report on Survey Findings* (Creative Center Charitable (CCC) Foundation).
- Promote Ukraine (2019) 'Support Group for Ukraine: Just Another Task Force?' <https://www.promoteukraine.org/support-group-for-ukraine-just-another-task-force/>
- Richter, M.M. (2023) 'Policy Advice Supply Chain in Ukraine' (PASCU), v. 1.0, Discuss Data.
- Samokhvalov, V. and Strelkov, A. (2021) 'Cross-dimensional Network of Democracy Promotion: Public Administration Reform in Post-Euromaidan Ukraine'. *Journal of European Integration*, Vol. 43, No. 7, pp. 799–814.
- Schimmelfennig, F. (2015) 'Europeanization Beyond Europe'. *Living Reviews in European Governance*, Vol. 10, No. 1, p. 34.
- Schimmelfennig, F. (2017) 'Beyond Enlargement: Conceptualizing the Study of the European Neighbourhood Policy'. In Schumacher, T., Marchetti, A. and Demmelhuber, T. (eds) *The Routledge Handbook on the European Neighbourhood Policy* (Routledge), pp. 17–27.
- Schimmelfennig, F. (2021) 'EU External Governance and Europeanization'. In Gstöhl, S. and Schunz, S. (eds) *The External Action of the European Union: Concepts, Approaches, Theories* (Bloomsbury Publishing).
- Schimmelfennig, F. and Sedelmeier, U. (2004) 'Governance by Conditionality: EU Rule Transfer to the Candidate Countries of Central and Eastern Europe'. *Journal of European Public Policy*, Vol. 11, No. 4, pp. 661–679.
- Schumacher, T. (2017) 'The European Neighbourhood Policy: The Challenge of Demarcating a Complex and Contested Field of Study'. In Schumacher, T., Marchetti, A. and Demmelhuber, T. (eds) *The Routledge Handbook on the European Neighbourhood Policy* (Routledge), pp. 3–13.

- Stegniy, O. (2011) 'Ukraine and the Eastern Partnership: 'Lost in Translation'?' *Journal of Communist Studies and Transition Politics*, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 50–72.
- Tomic, N. (2013) 'Coordinative Discourses in Brussels: An Agency-Oriented Model of EU Foreign Policy Analysis'. *Perspectives on European Politics and Society*, Vol. 14, No. 2, pp. 223–239.
- Transparency International (2021a) 'Supreme Court Overturns HACC's Conviction'. <https://ti-ukraine.org/en/news/supreme-court-overturns-hacc-s-conviction/>
- Transparency International (2021b) 'Who Is "Burying" Tatarov's Case? Timeline'. <https://ti-ukraine.org/en/news/who-is-burying-tatarov-s-case-timeline/>
- Van Schendelen, M.P. and Van Schendelen, R. (2010) *More Machiavelli in Brussels: The Art of Lobbying the EU* (Amsterdam University Press).
- Wolczuk, K. (2009) 'Implementation Without Coordination: The Impact of EU Conditionality on Ukraine Under the European Neighbourhood Policy'. *Europe – Asia Studies*, Vol. 61, No. 2, pp. 187–211.

List of Interviews

- Interview 1:** former European Union (EU) technical policy adviser, November 2021.
- Interview 2:** European Commission representative, December 2021.
- Interview 3:** Ukrainian civil society organization (CSO) representative, December 2021.
- Interview 4:** Ukrainian high-level government representative, January 2022.
- Interview 5:** Ukrainian CSO representative, December 2021.
- Interview 6:** EU technical policy adviser, November 2021.
- Interview 7:** Commission on Audit representative, November 2021.
- Interview 8:** EU member state technical adviser to Ukraine, December 2021.
- Interview 9:** representative of a Ukrainian research centre, November 2021.
- Interview 10:** Ukrainian high-level CSO representative, November 2021.
- Interview 11:** Ukrainian CSO representative, January 2022.
- Interview 12:** EU technical policy adviser, January 2022.